

ISic1417

I.Sicily inscription 1417

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

S. Giovanni Catacomb

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κεῖ
2. τε Ἰλάσιος
3. ζήσας ἔτη λ ἕ
4. κοιμήθη πρ(ὸ) γ εἰδῶ[ν]
5. Σεπτεμβρί
6. ων εἰρήνηεἰρήνη
7. σοι ἐν Χρ(ιστ)ῷ

Apparatus

Text from Curbera 1996

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644967

Bibliography

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